

ABU MANSUR MOTURIDI’S “TA’WILAT AL-QUR’AN” IN THE CONTEXT OF THEOLOGICAL ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

This article provides comprehensive information about the theological issues expressed by Abu Mansur Maturidi in his work “Ta’wilat al-Qur’an.” To make the discussion of theological matters more understandable for readers, references to several sources related to the topic are included, along with definitions and explanations of theological terms. It is noteworthy that Maturidi also utilized hadiths in his interpretation of the Qur’an.

Keywords: *Qur’an, verse, hadith, sunnah, theology, prophethood, cosmology, divine attributes, science of kalam, mutakallim.*

“Currently, Western and Turkish Orientalists are using terms like “Theology” in relation to the science of kalam¹.

In ancient theological books, it was not necessary to provide evidence for the existence of Allah. Scholars of that time were well aware that no one doubted the existence of Allah. Therefore, they often began their books with discussions on the oneness of Allah and the absence of partners. However, currently, all scholars writing on beliefs are particularly focused on proving the existence of Allah. Recently, due to various reasons, the denial of Allah’s existence has become more prevalent, which has compelled them to address this issue.

Proving the existence of Allah is considered a fundamental issue in the science of kalam. Other matters stem directly from faith in the existence of Allah. For a person who does not believe in the existence of Allah, discussing other theological issues is of no benefit whatsoever. For someone who does not believe in Allah, saying “Allah mentioned this in the Qur’an” or “The Prophet (peace be upon him) said this in a hadith” seems pointless. Therefore, only rational and scientific evidence can be useful in this context. Scholars provide proof of the existence of Allah using such rational and scientific arguments.

¹ Sheikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf. *Sunni Beliefs*. - Tashkent: Mavarannahr, 2005. - p. 66.

After proving the existence of Allah, it is also of great importance to establish His oneness (tawhid). In the Maturidi teaching, the issue of tawhid is given serious attention. In this context, responses are provided against those who liken Allah to shapes and bodies (mushabbihah and mujassimah) and against the Mu'tazilites who deny the eternal nature of Allah's essence and attributes.

The term “Tawhid” is a verbal noun (gerund) that denotes “to unify” meaning to attribute uniqueness to something and to deny its multiplicity. In the book “Qamus al-Muhit” it is stated: “Tawhid is the belief in the One and Only Allah”².

Several definitions have been given regarding the terminological meaning of tawhid. For instance, Muhammad Ahmad Badakhshani, in his commentary on “Aqidat al-Tahawiyah” defines tawhid as: “The belief that a person should protect themselves from all forms of associating partners with Allah and to believe that Allah has no partner, neither in His essence, nor in His attributes, actions, names, or rulings”³.

According to the Maturidi teaching, Allah undoubtedly exists, is one and unique, and has no equal or likeness. He is eternal in all His attributes. He is the creator of all worlds.

Abu Hafs Najm al-Din al-Nasafi states the following in his work “Aqidat al-Nasafiyyah”:

“He is the One who brings the universe into existence, the First and the Last, the Ancient, always living, capable of all things, knowledgeable of everything, hearing all voices, seeing all, willing what He desires, and intending what He wishes—this is Allah, the Most High”⁴.

In the Maturidi teaching, there are three types of evidence for the existence and oneness of Allah:

1. Textual Evidence (Qur'an and hadith);
2. Rational Evidence (Reflection);
3. Order and Harmony in the Universe (The universe is created with a specific order and system).

Nuriddin Subki states about the oneness of Allah: “Allah is one, and He has no partners. If there were two creators, and one wished to create a certain being while the other wished to destroy that very being, then either both of their wishes would have to be fulfilled or one of their wishes would have to be realized. The fulfillment of both wishes is impossible. If one of them succeeds in fulfilling their wish, the

² Abdulqadir Abdur Rahim. “Axioms of Belief.” “Hilol-Nashr”. Tashkent 2022. – P. 70.

³ Abdulqadir Abdur Rahim. “Axioms of Belief.” “Hilol-Nashr”. Tashkent 2022. – P. 70.

⁴ Al-Nasafi, Abu Hafs. Al-Aqidat al-Nasafiyyah. “Dar al-Bashair al-Islamiyyah” 1993. – P. 12.

other’s unfulfilled wish would be defeated. If one is defeated, they cannot be a deity...”⁵.

A similar method of presenting arguments can also be found in Abu Mansur Maturidi’s book “Tawhid”: “If one of them wishes for the existence of something, the other wishes for its non-existence. The same applies to permanence and transience. In such cases, there is contradiction and opposition between them”⁶.

In this work, Maturidi does not provide the chain of transmission (isnad) for the hadiths when explaining the verses; rather, he suffices with conveying their meanings. Additionally, he highlights the parts of the hadith that illustrate the intended purpose without writing them in full⁷.

If one wishes to provide both textual and rational evidence for the interpretation of a verse, they first cite a hadith or the words of a companion, and then express their own opinion. In Maturidi’s interpretation of the verses with hadiths, the following aspects can be observed:

- He only presents a small portion of the hadith's chain of transmission (isnad);
- Sometimes he simply states the meaning of the hadith;
- Occasionally, he analyzes by explaining a hadith similar to the one being discussed;
- In some instances, he mentions more than one hadith at once.

It can also be understood that Maturidi does not pay much attention to the authenticity of the hadiths but instead focuses on the essence and meaning of his thoughts. Generally, Maturidi prioritizes interpreting the Qur’an with the Qur’an itself, then with hadiths, and the words of the companions and successors. Furthermore, he uses his own reasoning and *ijtihad* to provide a deeper understanding of Islamic beliefs and jurisprudence. He does not promote thoughts or ideas that contradict or oppose Islamic teachings. In his commentary, he places more emphasis on reason and *ijtihad* than many of his contemporaries, analyzing the interpretations given by earlier scholars on the verses. The difference in his approach to commentary compared to those focused on reason lies in his extensive use of transmitted sources.

Furthermore, the scholar has also made efforts to interpret theological verses through hadiths. In the process of explaining these theological verses, he has presented the views of misguided sects and factions, providing refutations against them through hadiths. The names of almost all these groups are mentioned in his commentary, including: Mu’tazilites, Khawarij, Jahmites, Karromites, Shia,

⁵ Nuriddin Subki. *Al-Bidaya fi Usul al-Din*. – Egypt: Dar al-Ma’arif, 1969. – P. 40.

⁶ Moturidiy, Abu Mansur. *Kitab al-Tawhid*. – Beirut: Dar al-Sadir, Istanbul: Maktabat al-Irshad, 2001. – P. 86.

⁷ Moturidiy, Abu Mansur. *Ta’wilat al-Qur’an* – Istanbul, 2005. Vol. 1. – P. 331.

Qadariyya, Jabariyya, and Qarmatians. He mainly offers refutations against the Mu'tazilites on kalam issues.

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